

Optimization of Cationic Frontal Polymerization Experiments: An Analysis of Compositions, Reproducibility, and Materials

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SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS
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OVERVIEW OF THIS TALK

Frontal polymerization

Radical-induced cationic frontal polymerization

Motivation, experimental design/optimization

Data collection, formulation chemistry, mold design

WHAT IS FRONTAL POLYMERIZATION?

- ▼ Propagating localized reaction zone
- ▼ Vital: greater rate of heat production than heat loss
- ▼ One-pot formulations
- ▼ Cure on-demand
- ▼ Long pot lives
- ▼ Fast curing

Acrylate (free-radical) FP initiated via UV light

RADICAL-INDUCED CATIONIC FRONTAL POLYMERIZATION

3,4-epoxycyclohexylmethyl 3,4-epoxycyclohexane carboxylate (CE)

Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (BADGE)

- ▼ First described by Mariani et al. of an epoxy resin
- ▼ Onium salts (photoacid generators) + thermal frontal polymerization (FP)
- ▼ Counterion properties affect kinetics

p-(octyloxyphenyl)phenyliodonium hexafluoroantimonate (IOC-8)

Benzopinacol

1,1-Bis(tert-butylperoxy)-3,3,5-trimethylcyclohexane (Luperox® 231)

RICFP: LITERATURE APPLICATIONS

Carbon fiber composite RICFP from Sangermano et al.

Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (BADGE)

Effect of different fillers on Tran et al.

MOTIVATION

- Mechanistic model of radical-induced cationic frontal polymerization
- Use kinetic data from experiments

FORMULATION PREPARATION: MONOMER & INITIATOR

3,4-epoxycyclohexylmethyl 3,4-epoxycyclohexane carboxylate (CE)

Neopentyl glycol diglycidyl ether (NPDGE)

Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (BADGE)

p-(octyloxyphenyl)phenyliodonium hexafluoroantimonate (IOC-8)

trimethylolpropane triglycidyl ether (TMPTE)

1,1-Bis(tert-butylperoxy)-3,3,5-trimethylcyclohexane (Luperox[®] 231)

Luperox[®] P (tert-butyl peroxybenzoate)

FORMULATION PREPARATION: FIRST FRONTS

Increasing IOC concentration

Large amount of bubbles

Neopentyl glycol diglycidyl ether (NPDGE)

p-(octyloxyphenyl)phenyliodonium hexafluoroantimonate (IOC-8)

Luperox® P (tert-butyl peroxybenzoate)

FORMULATION PREPARATION: IOC OPTIMIZATION

Previous literature: pyrolysis of IOC → generation of benzene-based volatiles

Decreasing IOC Concentration

Previous Luperox P sample

DESIGN OF MOLDS

- ▾ Silicone mold (heat resistant up to 294 °C)
 - ▾ Can adapt to many different needs
 - ▾ Rapidly generate molds for studies of boundary conditions

DESIGN OF MOLDS

- Also possible: creation of wooden mold
 - Adaptable as well
 - Basswood, as shown here
 - Differences in thermal properties

Propagating front in wooden mold

DESIGN OF MOLDS: EFFECT ON FP

- Wooden mold: little uncured material left
- Silicone mold: much more uncured material remaining

Top: polymer after FP in wooden mold
Bottom: polymer after FP in silicone mold

After FP polymer removed

INITIATION OF FRONTS

- RICFP initiated with heat for our case
 - Decompose radical initiator → acid generation from IOC decomposition
 - w/ direct contact → found that initiation temp has little effect on velocity
 - Also results in longer time to stable front

< 1 mm nichrome

Insert metal plate to initiate the front from side

Resistive nichrome wire w/ direct current

OBSERVATION OF FRONTS: THERMOCOUPLES

- Insert thermocouples into resin
- Calculate velocity based on max dT/dt

Example plot temperature extracted by thermocouples

OBSERVATION OF FRONTS: IR CAMERAS

Left: Testo IR camera
Right: FLIR mobile IR camera
Equivalent formulations

OBSERVATION OF FRONTS: THERMOCOUPLE EFFECTS

- 8 thermocouples max (all type K)
 - 3 different brands:
 - 0.5 mm diameter, exposed wire type
 - 0.7 mm diameter, soldered tip
 - 0.35 mm diameter, twisted wire

THERMOCOUPLE EFFECTS

(approx. position of TCs)

▾ No significant difference in front stability

THERMOCOUPLE EFFECTS: FRONT TEMPERATURE

THERMOCOUPLE EFFECTS: NUMBER OF THERMOCOUPLES

1 phr IOC, 1 phr TPED, NPDGE			
# thermocouples	TCs used	Front velocity (cm/min)	Front temperature (C)
8	12345678	5.40 ± 0.08	256.7 ± 2.5
7	1234567	5.36 ± 0.12	256.3 ± 3.1
	2345678	5.43 ± 0.03	257.2 ± 1.6
6	123456	5.31 ± 0.08	259.6 ± 3.2
	234567	5.39 ± 0.07	256.8 ± 2.3
	345678	5.50 ± 0.08	258.1 ± 3.1
5	23456	5.32 ± 0.00	260.9 ± 2.2
	12345	5.40 ± 0.05	259.0 ± 4.5
	45678	5.51 ± 0.14	257.3 ± 2.7

After 4, within same range for velocities

OBSERVATION OF FRONTS: IR CAMERA

- Problem with IR camera: no length scale
 - Cannot calculate velocity based on observed position of the front
- Heat up using heat gun, polyester tape heats faster than copper

- Larger difference higher concentration IOC samples
- Provides data for front velocity at the boundary

FUTURE WORKS AND CHALLENGES: PURIFICATION

Another issue with front reproducibility:
monomer purity

4 bottles of NPDGE

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